

CHARACTERISTICS OF PARENTS AND THEIR BELIEFS ON EDUCATION: BASIS FOR CHILD SUPPORT PLAN

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Characteristics of Parents and their Beliefs on Education: Basis for Child Support Plan

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Abstract

This descriptive-correlational research delved into parental beliefs and their influence on children's education in Kabangahan II Elementary School, Sta. Cruz, Rogongon, Iligan City, Philippines. Results revealed that the parental beliefs in terms of parental education, parental income, and access to educational resources received a strongly agree as the overall weighted mean. It has been demonstrated that parents' attitudes about their children's education and interactions with them mirror their views and expectations about their learning and performance, which influences the child's motivating growth in the classroom. Notably, the study found no significant relationship between the respondent's profile and the parental beliefs of the respondents. Put another way, the study finds no discernible patterns or connections between the respondents' profile and their views on education for their children. Moreover, it implies that parental views on education are more unique and varied, impacted by a wide range of situations, values, and personal experiences as opposed to particular demographic characteristics. The analysis, based on the Chi-squared Test, revealed that there is no significant association between parental beliefs and their profile in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, and occupation. Moving on, the relationship between profile and parental beliefs based on Pearson's Correlation shows no significant relationship between profile and parental beliefs in terms of parental education, parental income, and access to educational resources. Lastly, a regression analysis incorporating respondents' profiles and parental beliefs indicated that neither respondent's profile significantly predicts parental beliefs.

Keywords: *parental beliefs, parental education, parental income, access to educational resources*

Introduction

One prevalent issue concerning parental beliefs is the existence of disparities in parental engagement and expectations. Conflicts and disagreements might arise when drafting a child support plan since many parents have different views and ideas about schooling. Divergent views amongst parents regarding education can lead to conflict and make it difficult for them to consistently support their child's academic needs. It can be difficult to develop a cohesive strategy, for example, if one parent values traditional schooling while the other favors homeschooling or alternative teaching techniques. Additionally, Parents remain an influential driving force for their child's motivational development, although the child's environment expands to include peers and teachers when starting school. Parents have a strong effect on their children's schooling, especially in terms of encouragement and expectations that they transmit to their children concerning the importance of education (Cheung & Pomerantz, 2018).

Parental beliefs and their influence on children's education are a pivotal aspect of educational research and practice. Parental beliefs include the attitudes, expectations, and ideals that parents have for their kids' education. These attitudes have a big impact on the home learning environment, which in turn shapes a child's motivation, work ethic, and general academic approach. On the other hand, a child's intellectual advancement may be hampered by unfavorable attitudes or low expectations. Regardless of one's beliefs, parental involvement—which includes engaging in educational practices at home, communicating with instructors, and participating in school activities—is a critical factor in determining academic outcomes.

According to DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2022, Titled “Omnibus Guidelines on the Regulation of Operations of Parent-Teacher Associations”. It states that the Department provided the updated operating manual of PTA, which will serve as a guide for the school-based organization in managing collaborative engagements among education stakeholders. In line with this DepEd Order, parents play a big part in the academic success of their children, by showing support and being actively involved in whatever activities agreed by the school and other stakeholders for the benefit of the children.

Therefore, there is a need to examine parental beliefs since the attitudes, expectations, and involvement of parents in their children's education are critical factors that influence students' learning experiences and results. This research aimed to clarify the complex relationships between parents' attitudes, expectations, and their children's academic success. The study aimed to contribute to evidence-based techniques for establishing a learning environment by identifying the elements of parental views that make a good or negative impact on academic success. The study was conducted in the S.Y. 2023-2024 and studied by Teacher I at Kabangahan II Elementary School.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the respondent's profile and parental beliefs in terms of parental education, parental income, and access to educational resources in Kabangahan II Elementary School. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

- 1.1. age;
- 1.2. sex;
- 1.3. highest educational attainment of parents; and
- 1.4. occupation?
2. What are the parental beliefs of the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1. parental education;
 - 2.2. parental income; and
 - 2.3. access to educational resources?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile and the parental beliefs?
4. How does the respondents' profile significantly predict parental beliefs?
5. What action plan can be designed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to describe the Characteristics of Parents and their Beliefs on Education: Basis for Child Support Plan. Descriptive-correlational studies describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them (Gabriel, 2020). Descriptive research is appropriate as it seeks to describe the current situation or condition of a phenomenon or problem. Correlational research, on the other hand, aims to establish a relationship between two or more variables. In a descriptive-correlational study, researchers first collect data through various methods such as surveys, and questionnaires, followed by descriptive statistical analysis such as frequency distributions, mean and standard deviation.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were 100 randomly selected parents of the learners who are enrolled in Kabangahan II Elementary School for the School Year 2023-2024. The total number of respondents is subject to answering the said questionnaire prepared by the researcher.

The random selection of participants was secured to ensure that the sample is representative of the population of the parents from Kabangahan II Elementary School. This method of sampling allowed the researcher to generalize the results of the study to the larger population. However, it is important to note that this study's findings may not be generalizable to other places or regions in the Philippines due to differences in context about parental beliefs.

To ensure the ethical considerations of the respondents, informed consent was obtained from the participants before their involvement in the study. The confidentiality of the participants will be maintained, and all data collected will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and only be used for research purposes.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Actual No. Of Respondents Per Grade Level</i>
Kindergarten	18	9
Grade 1	41	10
Grade 2	26	16
Grade 3	27	11
Grade 4	33	18
Grade 5	33	28
Grade 6	30	8
Total	208	100

Instrument

The survey questionnaire was used as the primary gathering tool for the data of this study. This study employed a researcher-made questionnaire was utilized to gather the data. The questionnaire utilized a 5-point Likert scale for rating, with values ranging from 5 to 1: 5 indicating strongly agree, 4 for agree, 3 for neutral, 2 for disagree, and 1 for strongly disagree. This questionnaire is used to generate data through evaluation, review for relevance and clarity, and validation to ensure that the instrument used will measure what is designed to gauge without any unnecessary confusion on the part of the one answering the items.

To ensure the robustness of the survey's validity and reliability, a panel of three (3) expert reviewers was engaged during the data collection phase. Their expertise was instrumental in evaluating the appropriateness and relevance of the research instrument. Their valuable suggestions and comments served as the foundation for refining the final version of the research instrument.

Concurrently, to assess the internal validity of the questionnaire, a pilot test was conducted among a group of 25 parents who were not part of the main study respondents. The pilot testing phase provided insights into the questionnaire's clarity, comprehensibility, and overall effectiveness before its implementation in the main study.

Table 2. *Reliability Analysis of Variables*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Number Of Questions</i>	<i>Cronbach Alpha</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Parental Education	10	0.859	Reliable
Parental Income	10	0.786	Reliable
Access To Educational Resources	10	0.865	Reliable

Table 1 presents the reliability analysis of variables. The result shows that the questionnaire consisted of 30 questions with a Cronbach Alpha value of greater than 0.700, which indicated that all questions were reliable. The threshold value in the literature is much higher than 0.700. This implied that the participating respondents clearly understood the research questions and similar questions were answered in the same direction.

Procedure

The selected parents from Kabangahan II Elementary School were provided with informed consent forms that explained the purpose of the study, the expected duration of the survey, the confidentiality of information shared, and the voluntary nature of their participation. The study adhered to ethical considerations, including obtaining consent, maintaining confidentiality, and ensuring voluntary participation.

Prior approval was sought from the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisor, and school principals. A systematic random sampling technique was used to select the parents from Kabangahan II Elementary School. The researcher scheduled appointments at the parent's convenience time to conduct the survey, and the data collected were analyzed using statistical software. Meanwhile, the academic performance of learners was based on their final ratings for the school year 2023-2024 and recorded through the Learner Information System (LIS). Confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were maintained throughout the study, and results were presented in aggregate form with no individual respondent information revealed.

Data Analysis

These statistical tools can help provide insights and interpretations of the data gathered from the study and can help answer the research questions and objectives.

For problem 1, Frequency and Percentage were used to identify the respondents' profile in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, and occupation.

Problem 2, Mean and Standard deviation was used to determine the parental beliefs of the respondents in terms of parental education, parental income, and access to educational resources.

For problem 3, the Chi-square Test was used to determine if there is a significant relationship between the profile and parental beliefs of the respondents.

For Problem 4, Linear regression analysis was utilized to test if the predictors significantly influence the profile and the parental beliefs of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered to answer the problems of the study. It also analyzes and interprets the data collected by the researchers to solve the issues in the study. The presentation, interpretation, and analysis were supported by tables and arranged in the same manner as the questions presented in the statement of the problem in Chapter 1.

Problem 1: What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, and occupation?

Table 3. *Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
15 – 20	2	2.0
21 – 30	14	14.0
31 – 40	44	44.0
41 – 50	27	27.0
50 and above	13	13.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3 presents the age of the respondents. The result showed that the largest percentage of respondents falls within the age range of 31-40, constituting 44.0% of the sample. This indicated that parents in this age group are likely a significant part of the surveyed population. On the other hand, the age group 15-20 represents the smallest percentage at 2.0%. The distribution of respondents across various age groups reveals a glaring difference, as this data displays. People in the age range of 31 to 40 make up a sizable portion of the population studied, which suggests that parents make up this group. In contrast, the tiny percentage of respondents in the sample who are between the ages of 15 and 20 suggests that there are fewer younger respondents overall. The age distribution discrepancy highlights the thirties and forties as a more common age group than teenagers and young adults, providing insight into the demographic

makeup of the population polled. This suggested that there might be limited insight into the beliefs and perspectives of parents with children in this age range.

According to Dewar (2017), respondents in their 30s and early 40s frequently manage a challenging stage of parenthood while juggling obligations to their families, their careers, and their financial security. It suggested that parents belonging to this age group might give priority to specific parenting philosophies, such as authoritative parenting, which is defined by warmth, support, and well-defined boundaries.

Table 4. *Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	42	42.0
Female	58	58.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4 displays the sex of the respondents. The result presented that the majority of respondents in this study are female, comprising 58.0% of the total sample. In contrast, male respondents constitute 42.0%. This indicated that the study might largely represent the experiences and perspectives of female parents compared to male parents. The study's gender difference is evident in the distribution of respondents by sex, where females are more common than males. This data implies that there is a higher representation of girls than males in the survey. To guarantee a varied and inclusive representation of different sexes, the data emphasizes how crucial it is to take gender balance into account in research projects.

As emphasized by Tocu (2018) parental beliefs relating to the rearing and education of children are influenced by the participants' gender and level of education. This suggested that females may be more likely to take part in parenting-related research since they are moms or other caregivers who are typically more involved in raising children.

Table 5. *Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Elementary level	32	32.0
Elementary graduate	25	25.0
High School level	30	30.0
High School graduate	13	13.0
College level	0	0
College Graduate	0	0
Total	100	100.0

Table 5 shows the educational attainment of the respondents. The result presented the highest percentage of respondents with 32.0% of the sample falling into the Elementary Level while the lowest percentage of 13.0% fell into High School graduates. The differences between the percentages of elementary and high school graduates show how respondents are distributed across different educational levels. The higher percentage of respondents in the Elementary Level category suggests that there are more younger people in the survey, while the lower percentage of High School graduates shows that there are fewer people who have finished their high school education. These data provide insight into the educational backgrounds of the population surveyed and highlight the disparities in educational attainment among respondents. It implied that a significant portion of the sample may have only completed elementary school or less formal schooling. Given that education level is frequently correlated with exposure to a variety of viewpoints, the development of critical thinking abilities, and the availability of resources, this may have an impact on their attitudes toward parenting.

According to GOP (2018) when assessing a family's socio-economic status, the mother's and father's education, employment, and combined income are all considered rather than just one parent's qualities alone. Parents with higher education levels may be exposed to a larger variety of parenting ideas and methods, whereas parents with lower education levels may rely more heavily on conventional or culturally embedded beliefs about raising children.

Table 6. *Occupation*

<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Farmer	85	85.0
Construction workers	15	15.0
Government employee	0	0
Others	0	0
Total	100	100.0

Table 6 presents the occupations of the respondents. The result revealed that the majority of respondents' occupations fall into farmers, constituting 85.0% of the total sample. Meanwhile, only 15.0% of the sample were construction workers. It implied that a distinctive lifestyle, including living in a rural area, putting in long hours, and having a strong connection to the land and community, is frequently associated with farming. According to Rank and Hirschl (2019). For all people and families, regardless of where they live, to have access to the opportunities and resources they require to better their socioeconomic status and quality of life, it is imperative to acknowledge and address the developing nature of suburban poverty.

Problem 2: What are the parental beliefs of the respondents in terms of parental education, parental income, and access to educational resources?

Table 7 displays the parental beliefs in terms of parental education. The result showed that the weighted mean of 3.64, categorized as "Strongly Agree," indicated an overall high level of implementation of parental beliefs. It suggested that there is a substantial degree of agreement between parents' beliefs and their actual behaviors. Regardless of their level of education, parents appear to strongly support and apply their beliefs in their parenting styles and methods, as indicated by the high-weighted mean.

Table 7. Parental Beliefs in terms of Parental Education

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Parents should actively participate or assist in their child's homework and school activities.	3.66	+	0.50	Strongly Agree
2. It is important for parents to encourage the love of learning in their children	3.74	+	0.46	Strongly Agree
3. Parents should communicate regularly with teachers to stay informed about their child's progress.	3.58	+	0.50	Strongly Agree
4. Providing a quiet and dedicated space for homework is important for a child's academic success.	3.68	+	0.49	Strongly Agree
5. Effective communication between parents and children about the importance of education is important.	3.54	+	0.51	Strongly Agree
6. Parents with higher education are more likely to provide effective homework support to their children.	3.69	+	0.46	Strongly Agree
7. It is beneficial for parents to attend parent-teacher conferences to discuss their child's academic performance.	3.57	+	0.50	Strongly Agree
8. Parents should guide their children in setting and achieving academic goals.	3.67	+	0.47	Strongly Agree
9. It is important for parents to share their own educational experiences with their children	3.63	+	0.49	Strongly Agree
10. Parents consider themselves responsible for encouraging the love of learning in their children.	3.68	+	0.47	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.64	+	0.28	Strongly Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.24 Agree, 1.75-2.49 Disagree, 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

With the highest mean value of 3.74 of the indicators examined, Indicator 2 stands out as a particularly strong indicator of the importance of instilling in their children a love of learning. The significance of fostering in their children a positive outlook on learning and intellectual development is widely acknowledged by parents, as this result highlights. A child's academic progress, personal growth, and lifelong learning journey can all be significantly impacted by nurturing a love of learning. Conversely, Indicator 7 displays the lowest mean value of 3.57, suggesting that parents are not quite in agreement with the advantages of seeing their child's academic progress during parent-teacher conferences.

Silinskas and Kikas (2019) indicated that perceived parental support for the child is related to increased task persistence in homework situations. This indicates that learners are more likely to persevere and maintain concentration on their schoolwork when they sense their parents' support.

Table 8. Parental Beliefs in terms of Parental Income

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Parents believe that their income level affects the quality of educational resources they can provide for their children.	3.30	+	0.75	Strongly Agree
2. Do you think that your income determines your child's potential for success?	3.59	+	0.55	Strongly Agree
3. Parents think that financial stability positively influences their child's overall well-being.	3.65	+	0.48	Strongly Agree
4. Parents believe that higher income contributes to a positive and conducive learning environment at home.	3.61	+	0.62	Strongly Agree
5. Parental income is an important factor that influences a child's academic success.	3.62	+	0.53	Strongly Agree
6. Providing financial support for extracurricular activities is a priority for parents.	3.60	+	0.51	Strongly Agree
7. Do you believe that your income affects your child's motivation to learn?	3.34	+	0.76	Strongly Agree
8. Parents think that higher income positively influences their child's overall happiness.	3.40	+	0.59	Strongly Agree
9. Children from low-income families may face challenges in developing positive teacher-student relationships.	3.21	+	0.73	Agree
10. It is important for parents to openly discuss the family's financial situation with their child.	3.63	+	0.49	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.50	+	0.28	Strongly Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.24 Agree, 1.75-2.49 Disagree, 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

Table 8 exhibits the parental beliefs in terms of parental income. The result showed that the weighted mean of 3.50, which falls into the category of "Strongly Agree," is revealed by analyzing parental views in connection to parental income. This indicates that parents generally responded strongly agree on the application of their beliefs, even when their income levels differ. The strong consensus

highlights parents' shared commitment to upholding their values in the upbringing and development of their children, even in the face of possible socio-economic disparities.

With the highest mean score of 3.65, Indicator 3 stands out and shows that parents strongly agree that financial stability has a beneficial effect on their child's overall well-being. This research confirms what many parents believe, which is that their children's physical, emotional, and social well-being are all greatly impacted by their financial stability. On the other hand, Indicator 9 has the lowest mean value of 3.21, indicating that parents are not in agreement with the difficulties that low-income children may have in forming positive relationships with their teachers and learners.

According to Cabrera et al., (2018), Parents who are well-educated and have a large income typically have more time and resources available to them to fully engage in their children's education. They are more likely to participate in school-related activities, volunteer at school, attend parent-teacher conferences, and offer academic support to their kids at home.

Table 9. Parental Beliefs in terms of Access to Educational Resources

Indicators	Mean	+	SD	Description
1. Parents believe that having educational resources at home has a positive effect on their child's learning.	3.64	+	0.48	Strongly Agree
2. It is important for parents to provide books and learning materials for their children.	3.68	+	0.49	Strongly Agree
3. Providing a quiet place to study is essential for a child's academic success, according to parents.	3.62	+	0.49	Strongly Agree
4. Parents give importance to the quality of educational facilities available to their children.	3.55	+	0.50	Strongly Agree
5. Parents believe that having a variety of educational toys positively influences their child's development.	3.56	+	0.50	Strongly Agree
6. Parents recognize financial barriers may affect a child's access to educational resources.	3.55	+	0.52	Strongly Agree
7. Parents think that regular visits to the library contribute to their child's educational progress.	3.61	+	0.51	Strongly Agree
8. It is important for parents to know and have access to educational events in their community.	3.64	+	0.48	Strongly Agree
9. Parents believe that participating in educational programs and workshops will benefit their children.	3.61	+	0.49	Strongly Agree
10. Children from low socioeconomic backgrounds may have limited access to scholarships and financial aid opportunities.	3.68	+	0.55	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.61	+	0.27	Strongly Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.24 Agree, 1.75-2.49 Disagree, 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

Table 9 presents the parental beliefs in terms of access to educational resources. The result showed that the weighted mean of 3.61, categorized as "Strongly Agree," indicated an overall high level of implementation of parental beliefs. This shows that the majority of participants are very much in favor of giving their children access to educational resources. In essence, parents are deeply devoted to giving their children the resources and chances necessary for learning and academic success.

With the highest mean score of 3.68 among the different indicators examined, Indicator 2 stands out. Regarding parents giving their children books and educational resources, this is an indicator. It means that parents should make it a top priority to make sure their children have access to learning resources like books and learning materials. In contrast, Indicator 4 mean score of 3.55 is the lowest. This indicator focuses on how much parents value the standard of the educational resources provided to their children. The lower mean score indicates that, although parents may still value educational facilities, they do not give it the same priority as giving out tangible resources like books and study tools.

According to Sean (2014), Families with higher incomes often have more money to spend on their kids' education. They can pay for private tutors, extracurricular activities, and educational supplies that can improve a student's academic performance. On the other hand, low-income families may find it challenging to buy their kids the necessary school materials, textbooks, and a quiet place to study.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile and the parental beliefs?

Table 10 displays the relationship between the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of parental education and the profile. The result showed that the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of parental education had a highly significant association with their profile in terms of educational attainment. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of parental education and the profile in terms of age, sex, and occupation was not rejected, while educational attainment was rejected.

In addition, the data did not support the conclusion that parental views about education were significantly influenced by age, sex, or occupation. The null hypothesis about educational attainment, however, was not accepted. This suggests that a substantial correlation existed between the educational attainment of the respondents and their parents' attitudes toward education. Stated differently, the

statistics indicated that respondents' views toward parenting and schooling were influenced by their educational attainment.

Table 10. *Relationship1 Respondents' Parental Beliefs in terms of Parental Education and Profile*

Variables	Parental Education		Remarks	Decision
	X2 (df)	p-value		
Age	30.079ns (40)	0.873	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Sex	6.166ns (10)	0.801	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Educational attainment	50.735** (30)	0.010	Significant	Reject Ho
Occupation	7.855ns (10)	0.643	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho

Note: 1 – based on Chi-squared Test, ** - $P < 0.01$, *** - $P < 0.001$, ns - $P > 0.05$, * - $P < 0.05$

According to Musarat et al. (2018), Parental education is the type of education acquired by parents from any educational institution and the type of certificates obtained from primary to higher level. This suggests that parents with greater educational attainment may be able to succeed in a variety of spheres of life and may also instill in their children the importance of education. Thus, parents' own and their children's lives can be greatly impacted by the degree of education they have received.

Table 11. *Relationship2 Respondents' Parental Beliefs in terms of Parental Income and Profile*

Variables	Parental Income		Remarks	Decision
	X2 (df)	p-value		
Age	46.723ns (48)	0.525	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Sex	11.453ns (12)	0.491	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Educational attainment	38.576ns (36)	0.354	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Occupation	18.034ns (12)	0.115	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho

Note: 2 – based on Chi-squared Test, ** - $P < 0.01$, *** - $P < 0.001$, ns - $P > 0.05$, * - $P < 0.05$

Table 11 presents the relationship between the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of parental income and the profile. The result showed that the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of parental income had no significant relationship with their profile. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of parental income and their profile, was rejected.

This implies that parental attitudes on income and how it affects raising children are largely constant among various demographic groupings. Notably, this study implies that other factors may have a bigger influence on forming parental attitudes, independent of the parent's history, even if income plays a part in parenting decisions. According to GOP (2018), when assessing a family's socioeconomic status, the mother's and father's education, employment, and combined income are all considered rather than just one parent's qualities alone. Some parents from higher socioeconomic backgrounds may think that having more money enables them to give their children more chances, such as extracurricular activities or good schools. Conversely, parents from lower socioeconomic origins may place greater emphasis on family support and resilience since they have fewer financial means. Considering the educational background, employment status, and income of both parents enables us to comprehend how socioeconomic status influences parents' perspectives on what constitutes a good upbringing.

Table 12 exhibits the relationship between the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of access to educational resources and the profile. The result showed that the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of access to educational resources had no significant correlation with their profile. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of access to educational resources and their profile, was rejected.

Table 12. *Relationship3 Respondents' Parental Beliefs in terms of Access to Educational Resources and Profile*

Variables	Access to Educational Resources		Remarks	Decision
	X2 (df)	p-value		
Age	47.055ns (44)	0.349	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Sex	10.345ns (11)	0.500	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Educational attainment	36.621ns (33)	0.304	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Occupation	10.920ns (11)	0.450	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho

Note: 3 – based on Chi-squared Test, ** - $P < 0.01$, *** - $P < 0.001$, ns - $P > 0.05$, * - $P < 0.05$

This indicates that parents' perspectives regarding the significance of providing their children with access to educational resources were consistent, irrespective of their backgrounds or demographic characteristics. Consequently, the null hypothesis—which proposed that there isn't any meaningful relationship between parents' perceptions of educational resources and their profile—was rejected.

According to Karemaker et al., (2017), studies have proven that parental behaviors and attitudes toward learning impact upon children's learning. That is, parental engagement is essential for improving educational outcomes. Children are inspired to take learning seriously and aim for achievement because of the supportive environment this interaction fosters. In the end, it is believed that parental belief is essential to assisting children in realizing their academic potential and preparing them for success in the future.

Problem 4: How does the respondents' profile significantly predict parental beliefs?Table 13. *Variables that best predict Respondents' Parental Beliefs in terms of Parental Education*

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	3.426	0.219		15.617	0.000
Age	0.016	0.029	0.054	0.540	0.591
Sex	0.059	0.066	0.105	0.902	0.369
Educational Attainment	0.072	0.028	0.269	2.529	0.013
Occupation	-0.077	0.096	-0.099	-0.801	0.425
R = 0.296	R ² = 0.088	F = 2.279	Sig. = 0.066		

Note: Based on Linear Regression, ** - $P < 0.01$, *** - $P < 0.001$, ns - $P > 0.05$, * - $P < 0.05$

Table 13 presents the variables that best predict respondents' parental beliefs in terms of parental education. The respondents' parental belief in terms of parental education was affected by the profile in terms of educational attainment. The significance of parental influence on children's educational outcomes is highlighted by the relationship found between parental education and beliefs. According to the findings, parents who have completed more education are more likely to impart to their kids a favorable outlook on education and academic achievement. This demonstrates how parental educational attainment shapes attitudes and ideas about education across generations within households. This implied that no variables affected the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of parental education.

The R² value of 0.088 implies that 8.8% of the variance in parental belief in terms of parental education can be explained by the profile of educational attainment. Hence, 91.2% of the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of parental education can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The regression analysis is not significant, with an F-value of 2.279 with a corresponding p-value of 0.066. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' parental beliefs in terms of parental education was not rejected.

A parent's educational attainment is one of the many important elements that might influence their ideas regarding education. Greater education can lead to more professional choices, higher earning potential, and greater social mobility, all of which parents who have higher education levels typically know directly. Their strong belief in the importance of education for their children is likely to result from this. It is noteworthy, nonetheless, that parental opinions are not only influenced by the educational attainment of the parents. Aside from these, other important determinants include access to resources, personal experiences, social status, and cultural background. For instance, regardless of their educational credentials, parents from cultures that place a high value on education may have strong opinions on its significance. Comparably, financially strapped parents could nevertheless place a high value on education even though they are unable to offer their children the same resources and support as more affluent parents.

According to Musarat et al. (2018), Parental education is the type of education acquired by parents from any educational institution and the type of certificates obtained from primary to higher level. But aside from formal education, some other factors also have a role in how involved parents are in their children's education. One major one is the availability of resources, such as sufficient funds or learning aids to help their children study. Personal experiences are important as well; their opinions regarding their children's education may be influenced by their own educational experiences or their interactions with the educational system. Both social positions, or one's place in society, and cultural background, which includes customs and beliefs, are significant.

Table 14. *Variables that best predict Respondents' Parental Beliefs in terms of Parental Income*

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	3.567	0.234		15.272	0.000
Age	-0.008	0.031	-0.027	-0.258	0.797
Sex	0.019	0.070	0.032	0.266	0.791
Educational Attainment	-0.012	0.030	-0.044	-0.401	0.689
Occupation	-0.038	0.102	-0.048	-0.372	0.711
R = 0.094	R ² = 0.009	F = 0.211	Sig. = 0.932		

Note: Based on Linear Regression, ** - $P < 0.01$, *** - $P < 0.001$, ns - $P > 0.05$, * - $P < 0.05$

Table 14 presents the variables that best predict respondents' parental belief in terms of parental income. The respondents' parental belief in terms of parental income was not affected by the profile. This implied that no variables affect the respondents' parental beliefs in terms of parental income.

The R² value of 0.009 implies that 0.9% of the variance in parental belief in terms of parental income can be explained by the profile. Hence, 99.1% of the respondent's parental beliefs in terms of parental income can be attributed to other variables not included in the

regression model.

On the other hand, the regression analysis did not find a significant relationship between the variables, with an F-value of 0.211 with a corresponding p-value of 0.932. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents’ parental beliefs in terms of parental income was not rejected.

The educational background, cultural values, life experiences, and social standing of parents are only a few of the variables that shape their opinions. Parental engagement or community resources are some additional ways that parents who place a high value on education can help their children's learning. Another option is for them to prioritize education regardless of their financial situation. However, parents who make more money could not place as much emphasis on education if they don't think it's important. Income, therefore, does not always affect parents' ideas and behaviors toward their children's education, even though it can play a part in providing resources for education. It is easier to recognize how complicated parenting influences are when one is aware of the variety of elements that go beyond financial status.

The influence of socioeconomic indicators on child development is important to understand, but so too is the broader association of these indicators with the availability of resources for individuals to make changes for themselves and their families. Indeed, we often find that indicators of SES are more closely associated with children’s achievement outcomes than are more proximal individual factors, such as cognitive skills like attention, working memory, and inhibition Ahmed et al., (2019).

According to Levin (2019), "socioeconomic status remains the most powerful single influence on students' educational and other life outcomes" (p. 75). That assertion does not place the blame for the family's socioeconomic situation on the family; rather, it is a compilation of several elements that are connected with low SES, such as the families' neighborhoods and the caliber of their schools and teachers. It shifts the focus of the discussion from condemning specific people or families for their socioeconomic status to understanding the linked components and structural causes of inequality. The multidimensional character of socioeconomic status must be addressed, and equity in opportunities must be promoted for all people, regardless of their socioeconomic background, to resolve these discrepancies.

Table 15 presents the variables that best predict respondents’ parental beliefs in terms of parental education. The respondents’ parental belief in terms of access to educational resources was not affected by the profile. This implied that no variables affected the respondents’ parental beliefs in terms of access to educational resources.

The R2 value of 0.048 implies that 4.8% of the variance in parental belief in terms of access to educational resources can be explained by the profile. Hence, 95.2% of the respondents’ parental beliefs in terms of access to educational resources can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

Table 15. *Variables that best predict Respondents’ Parental Beliefs in terms of Access to Educational Resources*

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	3.597	0.216		16.678	0.000
Age	-0.023	0.029	-0.081	-0.793	0.430
Sex	0.061	0.064	0.114	0.954	0.343
Educational Attainment	0.033	0.028	0.130	1.203	0.232
Occupation	-0.068	0.094	-0.091	-0.718	0.474
R = 0.219	R2 = 0.048	F = 1.199	Sig. = 0.316		

Note: Based on Linear Regression, ** - $P < 0.01$, *** - $P < 0.001$, ns - $P > 0.05$, * - $P < 0.05$

The regression analysis is not significant, with an F-value of 1.199 with a corresponding p-value of 0.316. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents’ parental beliefs in terms of access to educational resources was not rejected.

The respondents' profiles had no effect on the parents' opinions regarding the availability of educational resources. This indicates that parents' opinions regarding the accessibility of educational resources were consistent, irrespective of the respondents' identities or places of origin. The respondents' varied histories, locations, or personal traits had little effect on the parents' opinions toward schooling. This implies that parental perceptions of educational resources stayed stable and unaffected by outside variables such as the respondents' profiles.

Accordingly, the economic, social, and cultural capital of families is related to the academic achievement of their children. Families allocate and spend resources such as income, cash, knowledge, and time that they own and control as economic, social, and cultural capital to improve and enhance their children’s education, cognitive skills, and language proficiency. In compliance with the family investment model, families from higher socioeconomic status can provide their children with better educational materials and resources at home, especially books and magazines thanks to their wealth (Volodina, Heppt & Weinert, 2021). The number of books in the family home is often considered one of the various predictors of socioeconomic status (Rutkowski & Rutkowski, 2013) and is associated with

not only professional status and prestige but also cultural capital (Sieben & Lechner, 2019). The family cultural capital is particularly important for educational and academic achievement and can help promote, nurture, and enhance children's knowledge and skills (Evans et al., 2010).

Conclusions

In conclusion, the analysis of parental beliefs underscores commendable strengths in areas like parental education, parental income, and access to educational resources. Parental beliefs have a significant impact on their children's educational path, influencing their attitudes, goals, and eventually, their academic performance. Whether parents place a higher value on practical skills, academic performance, or a combination of the two, their attitudes have a big influence on how their children approach learning.

In examining the relationship between respondents' profiles and parental beliefs, the study reveals non-significant results. This suggests that the opinions parents have about their children's education are not significantly influenced by characteristics like age, occupation, or any other aspect of their profile. However, when it comes to educational attainment it had a significant association with their profile. Put another way, the study finds no discernible patterns or connections between the respondents' characteristics and their views on education for their children. Although this may come as a surprise, it implies that parental views on education are more unique and varied, impacted by a wide range of situations, values, and personal experiences as opposed to particular demographic characteristics. Consequently, it's important to acknowledge the distinctiveness of every family's viewpoint when examining how parents feel about their children's education rather than assuming that particular traits will dictate their opinions.

The following were the recommendations of the study:

Parents. Parents' beliefs have a big influence on how your child learns. Remain kind and encouraging, putting more emphasis on your child's interests and skills than on strict rules. Try to foster a positive learning atmosphere at home, talk to teachers, and pay attention to what they have to say.

School Administrators. Acknowledge how much parental ideas influence the experiences of students. Encourage parent-teacher collaboration by giving parents the tools and assistance they need to comprehend and actively participate in their child's education.

Learners. Recognize that your school experiences may be influenced by your parents' educational views. Share your needs and goals with them, and ask for help from teachers and counselors if necessary to overcome any obstacles that may come up.

Future Researchers. Consider the various aspects, such as cultural backgrounds, social conditions, and individual experiences, that affect parents' views regarding schooling. To create treatments and policies that encourage positive parental involvement in education, investigate the dynamic relationship between parental beliefs and student outcomes.

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